

NAZARETH MARGOSCHIS COLLEGE AT PILLAIYANMANAI,
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GREEN ENERGY & SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Foreword

Perhaps, it is because of my own early experience as a Commerce teacher for more than two decades, I read the articles presented in the book and found it very informative and useful to the research scholars and teachers. On reading these research articles, it occurred to me that this book offers a different insight to the field of Green Energy and Sustainable Development and also I affirm that it is a valuable addition to the presently existing knowledge; I am elated to learn this has now been done.

The book aims to bring together academia, manufacturers, engineers, and customers from all over the world to deliberate upon the challenges and opportunities faced by the Energy sector in the wake of dwindling natural sources and increasing concern over climate change. Further, it discusses the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted towards the development of green and sustainable technology. It is envisaged in the backdrop of India's vision - "Energy Independence and Power for all by 2023" and "Achieving renewable energy capacity by 2023".

This book provides a platform for discussion in various means of newer identity. I am happy to tell you that this highly commendable work is brought to you by PG and Research Department of Commerce, Nazareth Margoschis College at Pillaiyanmanai, Nazareth. I wish the team of editors all success in their venture.

Dr. Revathy B

Dean of Arts, Professor & Head
Department of Commerce,
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University.

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HOMEMAKERS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS GREEN BANKING -WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ONLINE PAYMENTS

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Abstract

This paper presents the Homemakers perception towards green banking with special reference to online payments. The main focus of the paper is to analyse the awareness level of the Homemakers regarding various online payments and transactions. Every aspect of life is going digital, and the finest illustration of this is that we are working to transition to cashless societies. A cashless society is one in which no transaction is made with cash; instead, everything is done digitally. The data for the study has been collected from 50 Homemakers in Palayamkottai. Various statistical tools are used for analysis purpose and it is found that the Homemakers are well aware of online payments and transactions. After the Demonetization of the Government on 2016, our country has also started getting steered towards a cashless society. This paper is an attempt to study the barriers, satisfaction towards online payments and transactions by Homemakers.

Key words: *Homemakers, Perception, Online payments.*

INTRODUCTION

Green banking is the practice that is environmental friendly and reduces bank's carbon footprints. One of the important green banking practice is online transaction. Every aspect of life is going digital, and the finest illustration of this is that we are working to transition to cashless societies. A cashless society is one in which no transaction is made with cash; instead, everything is done digitally. In India, all the transactions were once made in cash, but after the government's demonetization in 2016, our nation has likewise begun to move towards the direction of a cashless society. Online payments refer to making purchases of products without using actual currency. Online payments, as the name suggests, cover all financial transactions made using electronic

devices such computers, smart phones, tablets, smart watches etc. The online payment application came into the limelight like Paytm, Google pay, Phone pe, etc. The first credit card was released in 1980 by the Central of India. NEFT was adopted in 2005 and the country's first e-wallet, Oxigen Wallet, was released in July 2004 before. The purpose of this study is to understand the awareness level of Home maker's towards online payment. The government has taken initiative to create a cashless society and the role of home makers is significant in it.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The main drawback in online payments is Low Network issues. Without our acknowledgement our account details may traced by unknown websites due to online purchasing. The transfer of amount may delay while doing the transactions. The message notification for amount transaction will be received later. During the transaction, unpredictably our payments will be failed unreasonably.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to assess the online payment perception among home makers. To suggest positive and effective measures to strengthen the online payment transactions among home makers.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Only the region of Palayamkottai is included in this study. The investigation is also restricted by time and money. Personal bias is a possibility, and the accuracy could change in the future.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study about the barriers for Homemakers in online payments.
- To study the awareness level of the Homemakers regarding various online payments transactions.
- To measure the level of satisfaction towards online payment transactions by Homemakers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

V. Sanjai et al (2021) It has been shown that both online and in-person purchases are increasingly being made using online payment methods. This study has explored the problems with online payments as well as the adoption of electronic commerce for consumer payment. Also, customers who are forming a habit of using mobile payments are becoming more trusting as a result of technological improvements that support them and make them more convenient and transparent.

Dr. C. Mallesha (2020) This study looks at how customers in urban and rural areas perceive the adoption of online payment systems and how it affects Indian banking clients. The combined data tells us something crucial: in order to bridge the divide between rural and urban areas, rural residents needed more usage education and awareness. Results from the data show that both urban and rural customers use online payment for purchases, bill payments, and cash transactions.

Prof. Sana Khan et al (2018) her research suggests that the widespread usage of smartphones has contributed to the rising popularity of online payments. The trust that people have in electronic payments has grown over time. Most users, it has been noticed, make purchases because of the convenience and discounts. It has been observed that the benefits of e-payment methods are commonly linked to those offered by smartphones.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted for homemaker satisfaction towards online payments. The research approach is qualitative in nature. Since the behavior of the people involved and the situation is based on experience formation.

DATA COLLECTION

Primary data are those that the investigation gathers for our use for the first time. Our study will use a questionnaire as the main source of data, giving it an original flavour. Primary data for the study was gathered from samples utilising questionnaires and in-person interviews. Secondary data are collected from websites, periodicals, and journals.

SAMPLE SIZE

Sample size of my study is 50.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

For this study, a convenience sampling strategy has been used. Samples are chosen at the researcher's convenience.

STATISTICAL TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS:

In this study, statistical tools like percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, and chi-square are utilised to analyse the primary data

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION:

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

FACTORS	PARTICULARS	FFREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age	18 to 25	40	80
	26 to 35	5	10
	36 to 45	2	04
	Above 46	3	06
Qualification	SSLC	9	18
	HSC	7	14
	Under Graduation	28	56
	Post Graduation	6	12
Monthly Income	Below 20000	27	54
	20000 – 30000	6	12
	30000 – 40000	12	24
	Above 40000	5	10

Knowing about online Payments	Advertisements	12	24
	Friends/Relatives	23	46
	Bank promotion	3	06
	Own knowledge	17	34
Awareness about Online Payments	Yes	41	82
	No	9	18
Mode of payment transaction	Card transactions	13	26
	By scanning QR Code	12	24
	By using UPI ID	17	34
	Specific app payments	8	16
Safety of Online payment	Yes	42	84
	No	8	16
Receiving notification	Immediately	14	28
	Few hours later	21	42
	Within 2 to 3 days	15	30
	Never received	-	-

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that

- Majority 80% of the respondents belong to the age between 18 to 25.
- Majority 56% of the respondents have completed their UG degree.
- Majority 54% of the respondents income is less than 20000 per month.
- Majority of the respondents came to know online payment from their friends and relatives
- Majority 34% of the respondents use UPI ID for Online payments transactions.
- Majority 84% of the respondents think Online payment transactions are Safe

- Majority 42.9% of the respondents says that they receive notification after few hours of transactions.

PURPOSE OF USING ONLINE PAYMENT

Particulars	7 (23)	6 (35)	5 (43)	4 (50)	3 (57)	2 (66)	1 (78)	No. of respo	Score	Avg. score	Rank
Food delivery	5 (115)	6 (210)	9 (387)	5 (250)	6 (342)	4 (264)	15 (1170)	50	2738	54.76	I
For cloth/ accessories/ electronic purchase	5 (115)	4 (140)	9 (387)	5 (250)	8 (456)	6 (369)	13 (1014)	50	2731	54.62	II
Bill payments	6 (138)	7 (245)	12 (516)	3 (150)	10 (570)	2 (132)	10 (780)	50	2531	50.62	VI
Groceries	5 (115)	9 (315)	11 (473)	6 (300)	7 (399)	3 (198)	9 (702)	50	2502	50.04	VII
School/college fees	3 (69)	12 (420)	11 (473)	2 (100)	5 (285)	2 (132)	15 (1170)	50	2649	52.98	IV
Online ticket booking	4 (92)	11 (385)	8 (344)	4 (200)	6 (342)	6 (396)	11 (858)	50	2617	52.34	V
Transfer money	3 (69)	4 (140)	18 (774)	2 (100)	6 (342)	4 (264)	13 (1014)	50	2703	54.06	III

Source: Primary data

Garrett ranking method is used to analyse the purpose of using online payment among the respondents. The above table clearly stated that majority of the respondents use online payment mode for buying online food followed by purchasing Cloth/ Accessories and for fund transfer.

REASON FOR PREFERENING ONLINE PAYMENT

Reasons	Mean	Std. Deviation
Time saving	4.50	.839
Convenient	4.28	.970
More Discount and offer	3.70	.909
Easy to track	4.00	1.030
24*7 transfers	4.02	1.059

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains about the reasons for preferring online payment among the respondents. Based on the mean value it is understood that majority of the respondents prefer online payment to save time and it is convenient to make payment anywhere and at any time. Mostly Home makers make their children's school fees through online that save their time and it is convenient for them to make payment.

BARRIERS IN ONLINE PAYMENT

Barriers	Mean	Std. Deviation
Transaction failure	2.26	1.382
Fraud or theft	2.20	1.212
Security issues	2.24	1.333
Privacy issues	2.16	1.235
Transaction charges	2.32	1.362
Network issues	2.60	1.525

Source: Primary data

This table interprets the barriers in online payment, based on the mean score it is understood that majority of the respondents consider Network issue as the major barrier in the online payment followed by transaction charges and transaction failure. Due to these issues they are little bit scared of making online payment. If any mistakes happen due to these issues it takes time for them to get the amount refunded. That creates a mental agony for them.

FACTORS OF SATISFACTION

FACTORS	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SDA	Total score	Average score	Rank
Easy to navigate	15 (75)	23 (92)	6 (18)	5 (10)	1 (1)	196	39.2	III
Easy to understand	11 (55)	28 (112)	9 (27)	0 (0)	2 (2)	196	39.2	III
Easy to make payment	22 (110)	17 (68)	9 (27)	0 (0)	2 (2)	207	41.4	I
Easy to transfer	20 (100)	20 (80)	6 (18)	2 (4)	2 (2)	204	40.8	II
Easy for enquiry	9 (45)	19 (76)	18 (54)	0 (0)	4 (4)	179	35.8	V
Services are safe to use	9 (45)	18 (72)	18 (54)	2 (4)	3 (3)	178	35.6	IV

Source: Primary data

The above table represents the various factors that influence their satisfaction. From the above it's clearly understood that majority of the respondents feel that it is very easy to make online payment followed by easy to transfer and easy to understand. Mostly nowadays people prefer comfort and convenience and the online payment provides the same therefore they are highly satisfied.

H₀1: There is no significant association between respondents' age and their level of satisfaction towards online payment.

Age	Level of satisfaction			Total	Chi square	P value
	Low	Moderate	High			
18 -25	12	18	10	40	13.819	0.032
26 – 35	0	5	0	5		
36 - 45	0	0	2	2		
Above 46	0	1	2	3		
Total	12	24	14	50		

Source: Primary data

Chi square is used to analyse whether there is an association between respondents' age and their level of satisfaction towards online payment. Since the p value is less than .050, the hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore there is an association between the respondents' age and their level of satisfaction towards online payment. From the above table it is clearly understood that the respondents' between the age group of 18 - 25 have high level of satisfaction when compared to the others. Because they are more open to technology than the other set of people.

H₀2: There is no significant association between respondents' Educational qualification and their level of satisfaction.

Education Qualification	Level of satisfaction			Total	Chi square	P value
	Low	Moderate	High			
SSLC	1	4	4	9	2.718	.843
HSC	2	4	1	7		

Under Graduates	8	13	7	28		
Post Graduates	1	3	2	6		
Total	12	24	14	50		

Source: Primary data

Chi square is used to access the association between repondents' age and their level of satisfaction towards online payment. Since the p value is more than .050, the hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore there is no association between the respondents' Educational qualification and their level of satisfaction towards online payment.

H₀3: There is no significant association between respondents' Monthly income and their level of satisfaction.

Monthly Income	Level of satisfaction			Total	Chi square	P value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Below 20,000	7	11	9	27	6.481	.371
20,000 – 30,000	3	3	0	06		
30,000 – 40,000	1	8	3	12		
Above 40,000	1	2	2	05		
Total	12	24	14	50		

Source : Primary data

Chi square is used to analyse the association between repondents' monthly income and their level of satisfaction towards online payment. Since the p value is more than .050, the hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore there is no association between the respondents' Monthly income and their level of satisfaction towards online payment.

SUGGESTIONS

Sometimes online payment transactions may be failed due to lagging network services. It will be best if they update the lagging network service issues. The pop up alert of SMS notifications have been delayed for a day or two days. If the SMS pop up arrive at the right time it will be good for homemakers to check the transactions process. So the SMS notifications system should be upgraded. Some of the online payment apps and websites doesn't have a verified encryption to make transactions. It will leak our personal information and confidential account details will be drop out. So, our suggestion to all online payment apps and websites is to strengthen the security level.

CONCLUSION

This study is about Homemakers perception towards online payment transactions. This includes the barriers, purpose, and preference of online payment. Homemakers are the one who prefer 98% online payment transactions. It is good to hear many females are using digital payment nowadays. But there are so many fraudulence and thefts activity. The common drawbacks in online payment transactions are security issues, delayed notification alert, network issues, transfer charges and so on. These outcomes would help all the online payment apps to improve its service to their customers and Homemakers can access much easy.

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